

EARLY PREDICTION OF CRACK DEVELOPMENT USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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Introduction

- A fundamental aspect of composite materials research is understanding how they fail - the basic principles of this are well understood and can be found in a good text book. However, three rounds of the World Wide Failure Exercise have shown how difficult it can be to model the failure of composite materials.
- Physical experiments remain at the heart of determining the properties of composite materials.
- Digital image correlation (DIC), is a form of non-contacting extensometry. The current work employs DIC as a means to investigate the formation of cracks within [0/90]_s GFRP cross-ply composites.
- Can DIC accurately predict the onset and growth of transverse cracking, with particular emphasis on how early the predictions can be made.
- Can DIC identify key occurrences or features within the surface strain field that indicate signs of crack formation?

Materials and Methods

- [0/90]_s cross-ply laminates were produced using a frame-wound, wet layup route.
- The specimens were placed in an Instron 5982 electromechanical test frame, with a 100 kN load cell, and gripped using wedge-action grips suitable for tensile testing.
- An optimized speckle pattern was printed onto self-adhesive transfer paper and applied to the specimens.
- DIC images were captured using a single, dual-camera system using two 9 MPx Manta G-917B cameras
- The cameras were controlled via a Correlated Solutions master/slave controller connected to a VIC-3D control system.
- The DIC aspects of the experiment were carried out with reference to 'A Good Practices Guide for Digital Image Correlation'
- Analysis of the data was carried out using VIC 3D, and a comparison between the default settings of a subset of 29 pixels and a step size of 11 was carried out with revised settings of a 39 pixel subset and a step size of 12.

Figure 1 The experimental setup featuring the use of two light sources incident at an angle to the specimen contrasted against a white background.

Crack Density: Reality vs Prediction

Figure 2 – A comparison of theoretical crack growth and experimental results for (a) 2 mm specimens and (b) 4 mm specimens. In each case, specimen 1 is represented by ♦ and specimen 2 is shown as •. Standard error is represented by error bars.

Discussion

- Multiple instances of the development of strain minima were associated with cracks formed at above average crack onset loading, while strain maxima were found to be linked with cracks formed at below average onset loads.
- Progressive formation of inflection points and kinks to within ± 0.224 mm of the actual location of cracking in successive profiles were also observed, with the most noticeable changes occurring within profiles plotted just before the crack onset. After which, profiles maintain these changes with each consecutive load case following fracture.
- Identification of these characteristics can be found on average as early as 11.5 kN prior to the onset of transverse cracking, but this was often the case for only those formed at higher than average onset loading. Those that initiate below this threshold can usually be detected as early as 3.90 kN prior to damage.
- Contrary to the initial prediction of the formation of strain concentrations above the immediate area of transverse ply cracking, it was found that instances of peak strain have been translated across the surface of the longitudinal ply being analysed. It was suspected that the cause of this phenomenon was due to the difference in Poisson's ratio between the transverse and longitudinal plies. It further appeared to have a greater effect on thicker laminates. leading to the formation of strain "envelopes", instances where distinctive peak strain was bound between the two neighbouring cracks.
- Finally, the effect of increasing the subset and step sizes from 29 pixels and 7 pixels respectively to the suggested values of 39 pixels and 11 pixels in VIC 3D produced a loss of finer detail of the strain profiles. Many small scale distinguishing variations were found to have been masked by the dominant large scale spikes and drops in strain, while only reducing consumption of computational resources by a marginal amount.

Full Field Strain Maps

Figure 4: Examples of recorded surface strain fields with increasing load: (a) the magnified 2 mm test, shows the initial development of localised strain concentration contours around the area of eventual crack formation. These isolated developments then show signs of coalescing with characteristic bunching of iso-lines, leading to a small area of stress concentration at the onset of cracking in the final image. Series (b), the magnified 4 mm test, shows similar behaviour as load was increased. However, the localised strain concentrations coalescing did not signify the beginnings of crack formation in the immediate area. Instead the strain continued to grow away from the initial crack until the formation of another crack, effectively closing off the large area of stress concentration forming a containment of stress between subsequent cracks.

Strain Field Profile

Figure 4 Example of strain field profile: magnified 2 mm trial. Dash-dot lines represents the location of cracks in the transverse ply at the end of the test. Successive curves represents data captured for (a) at 2.5 kN (1), 5 kN (2), 7.5 kN (3), 10 kN (4) and 15 kN (5) and (b) 6-8.5 kN loading in intervals of 0.5 kN

Concluding Remarks

In some respects, the process has not been as effective as had been hoped, and it was not possible to detect every single crack prior to its onset. However, strain concentrations associated with cracking events were observed and it is hoped that further investigation will help to link these observations with physical phenomena in order to assist with early warning of cracking in composite components. Efforts to investigate the strain field around a single crack, prior to the crack forming are warranted.

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